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Studies on Mechanism of Ylide Initiated Radical Copolymerisation of Methyl Methacrylate with Styrene

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THREE mechanisms, namely (i) ternary molecular complex, (ii) cross-propagation and (iii) complexed radical, have been proposed for the copolymerisation of vinyl monomers in presence of Lewis acids. The copolymerisation of such monomers in the presence of ylide is relatively new discipline of polymer science and a few publications in this area have recently¹⁻⁴ appeared.

Experimental

The experimental details for present system have already been published elsewhere⁵. The polymerisations were carried out at 60° by employing modified dilatometric apparatus⁶ for 3 h under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The dilatometer was filled with the required amount of monomer and β -picolinium-*p*-chlorophenacylide (β -PCPY) in carbon tetrachloride. The copolymer was fractionated with acetonitrile and cyclohexane to remove homopolymers of methyl methacrylate (MMA) and styrene (Sty), respectively, but no detectable weight loss has been observed. The nmr, ir and esr spectra have been recorded with Varian 100 HA spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer 377, and E-line century series 109 (X-band) spectrometers, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data⁵

$$R_p \propto [\beta\text{-PCPY}]^{0.4} [\text{MMA}]^{0.75} \frac{1}{[\text{Sty}]^{0.4}}$$

inhibitory effect of hydroquinone and gyromagnetic value indicate that copolymerisation of MMA with Sty, initiated by β -PCPY (ylide), proceeds by a free radical mechanism.

The nmr spectra have been used to elucidate the composition and reactivity ratio of copolymers. The peak area due to phenyl protons of Sty and methoxy protons of MMA have been used to calculate the copolymer composition, which helped to evaluate reactivity ratio using Fineman-Ross method as 0.22 (r_1) and 0.30 (r_2) for the present system. These values match well with those

reported for radical copolymerisation⁷. No detectable weight loss and reactivity ratio supports the alternate nature of copolymer. The esr spectra (Fig. 1) of polymerisation mixture shows characteristic band at 3300 gauss, which confirms radical mode of polymerisation. The gyromagnetic ratio (g) calculated is 2.002.

Fig. 1. Esr spectra of polymerisation mixture (β -PCPY, AN and Sty in CCl_4); scan range = 5 kG, field set = 3300 G, modulation amplitude = 2×1 G, modulation frequency = 100 kHz, temp. = 20°, and microwave frequency = 9.385 GHz.

In case of ternary molecular complex (charge transfer complex) mechanism, it is well reported that electron-acceptor monomer forms binary complex⁸ with Lewis acid. This complex in turn forms charge transfer complex with electron-donor monomer as evidenced by the appearance of a new absorption band⁹ in the range of 300–360 nm in uv spectrum in case of copolymerisation of MMA with Sty.

In the present case, a comparison of ir spectra of polymerisation content (Fig 2) (β -PCPY with MMA in CCl_4) and MMA show that there is no shifting in the position of bands due to ester group. This rules out the possibility of formation of complex between β -PCPY and MMA. Similarly, a comparative study of uv spectra of polymerisation mixture showed no additional absorption band at 300–360 nm, which excludes the possibility of formation of charge transfer complex. Therefore, the present system does not proceed through charge transfer complex mechanism.

In case of radical complex mechanism, the radical end of the acceptor monomer unit is postulated to be stabilised by complexing with Lewis acid and to be capped with the donor monomer

Fig. 2. IR spectra of dilatometric content recorded after 6 min using $1.02 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ of $[\beta\text{-PCPY}]$ and 2.58 mol^{-1} of $[\text{AN}]$ in CCl_4 at 60° .

resulting in a radical complex, which is attached by the complex of acceptor monomer with Lewis acid to form a double complex with resonance among the radical and monomers. As discussed earlier no complex formation takes place, hence the possibility of polymerisation through complexed radical mechanism is also ruled out.

We have already reported¹⁰ that the $\beta\text{-PCPY}$ fails to initiate the polymerisation of Sty, however it accelerates. The radical polymerisation, which suggests that the tendency to form H^\cdot through $\beta\text{-PCPY}$ and Sty, is nil.

Consequently, it is proposed that the copolymerisation proceeds through cross propagation mechanism as evidenced by the following description. The radical generation process can be explained on the basis of the fact that $\beta\text{-PCPY}$ (ylide) dissociates to a triplet carbene (a)¹¹ which acts as a source of radicals. The triplet carbene reacts with monomer (MMA) to form a diradical (b)^{12,13} which further decomposes into two radicals (c) and (d). The values of reactivity ratio as 0.22 (r_1) and 0.30 (r_2) suggest that the MMA^\cdot radical (M_1^\cdot) is obtained by the reaction between H^\cdot and MMA. M_1 has much greater tendency to combine with Sty molecule rather than MMA, thereby producing MMA-Sty (M_2). Similarly, tendency of combination of M_2 with MMA is two times greater than that with Sty monomer. Thus it explains no appreciable weight loss of copolymers after refluxing with non-solvents to remove their corresponding homopolymers, therefore, alternate copolymer is obtained. The mechanism can be expressed as in Scheme 1.

(A) Radical generation and initiation :

(B) Propagation :

(C) Termination :

Scheme 1

On the basis of the above discussion, it is concluded that β -PCPY (ylide) initiated polymerisation results in the formation of an alternate copolymer, whereas conventional radical initiator like AIBN, benzoyl peroxide etc. gives alternating copolymer only in combination with Lewis acid otherwise random copolymer.

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Dye-sensitised Photooxygenation of Thioacetamide by Singlet Oxygen

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CARCINOGENIC compounds mainly fall into the following groups : polycyclic aromatics, aromatic amines, azo compounds, biological alkylating agents, metallic substances and some thio compounds. Thioacetamide has been reported to induce bileduct proliferation in rats often culminating in

cancer¹. A survey of the literature reveals the investigation on oxidation of thioamides²⁻⁹, however, no attention has been paid to the photochemical oxidation of primary thioamides and therefore, the present work was undertaken.

Experimental

Thioacetamide (Loba) was used after purification. An alcoholic solution of fluorescein dye (CI no. 45350) of concentration $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ was used in all experiments. Double-distilled water was used to prepare all the solutions.

All the reactions were carried out in a Corning vessel of capacity 500 ml. A 500 W tungsten lamp (Sylvania) was used in all the experiments for irradiation purpose. An aerator was used for bubbling air through the solution. Air served two functions: (i) generation of singlet oxygen in the presence of sensitizer and light and (ii) continuous stirring of the reaction mixture.

Pure thioacetamide (0.5 g) was dissolved in water (100 ml) and an alcoholic solution (4.0 ml) of fluorescein dye was added, so that the concentration of dye in the reaction mixture remained $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$. The pH of the solution was kept 7.0 before irradiation. The solution was then irradiated with the tungsten lamp maintaining a distance of 20 cm between the lamp and the lower surface of the reaction vessel. Air was continuously bubbled through the solution during the experiment. The progress of the reaction was followed by continuous tlc experiments and by measuring changes in pH at an interval of 30 min. It was found that reactions was initiated after approximately 8 h of irradiation, when some amorphous solid started separating from the reaction mixture. The amorphous substance was collected and analysed. During the irradiation, continuous tlc experiments with the supernatant liquid indicated only a single spot on the tlc plate corresponding to the original thioacetamide. As the reaction progressed intensity of the spot decreased and similar trend was observed in case of pH of the reaction mixture.

Dye-sensitized photooxygenation of thioacetamide was carried out at pH=9.0 in aqueous medium. The solid obtained was isolated which was found identical with the previously isolated substance. The alkaline solution attained acidic behaviour as the reaction proceeds.

The participation of singlet oxygen in the reaction was confirmed by using different singlet oxygen scavengers like DABCO, β -carotene, α -tocopherol, nickel chloride and cobalt chloride. The results are reported in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

In all the experiments, sulphur, acetic acid, ammonia and sulphuric acid were detected as

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SINGLET OXYGEN SCAVENGERS
[Fluorescein] = $4.0 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Scavenger] = $1.0 \times 10^{-6} M$

Scavenger*	Yield of the product (%)
—	24.0
Nickel chloride	0.5
Cobalt chloride	Nil
β -Carotene	0.3
DABCO	Nil
α -Tocopherol	0.2

*Refs. 10–12.

products. These products were identified by different physical, chemical and spectral methods.

The amorphous solid was recrystallised as yellow octahedral crystals (24.0%). It was detected as sulphur, m.p. 118° ; the crystals were treated with aqueous NaOH and a drop of $KMnO_4$ was added, which rapidly decolourised indicating the formation of thiosulphate in the solution. This solution was treated with lead acetate when black precipitate of lead sulphide was obtained, thereby showing the presence of sulphide ions and hence, sulphur. In addition to the above test, the solid product gave all other characteristic tests of sulphur. The other products, ammonia, sulphuric acid and acetic acid were identified by their usual tests with Nessler's reagent, barium chloride and ferric chloride, respectively. On the basis of the experimental observations, a tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photooxygenation of thioacetamide by singlet oxygen.

Singlet oxygen first attacks the thioacetamide to give dioxetane (I), which undergoes decomposition^{1,5} to give acetamide and sulphur monoxide.

The formation of dioxetane in this reaction is in agreement with the earlier observations^{1,6}.

Sulphur monoxide is a very short-lived species and it disproportionates to give sulphur and sulphur dioxide^{1,7}.

The formation of sulphuric acid may be due to the dissolution of SO_2 in water,

Acetic acid and ammonia might have been produced in the reaction by the hydrolysis of acetamide.

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of 4-oxa isomer, the C₂-protons would have appeared at much higher field⁶. C₄-protons being devoid of any vicinal hydrogen appeared as two doublets^{7,8} (see Experimental).

Similar treatment of 2 provided methyl 6-oxa-5-oxo-3,5-seco-4-nor-B-homocholestan-3-oate (6) and 3-oxa-4-oxo-4a,5-oxido-5ξ-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (7). The compound 6 gave negative Beilstein test and its spectral data (ir and pmr, see Experimental) were compatible with the structure 6. Formation of the compound 6 indicates that it follows the same mechanistic route (Scheme 1) as reported¹ in the case of its 6β-bromo analogue.

Perbenzoic Acid Oxidation of some 3-Oxosteroids

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IN continuation to our work on the synthetic steroids¹⁻³, the Baeyer-Villiger oxidation of some 3-ketosteroids, such as 3-oxo-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (1), 3-oxocholest-4-en-6β-yl chloride (2)⁴ and 3-oxocholesta-1,4-diene (3)⁵ has been presently undertaken to evaluate the effect of neighbouring substituent on the product outcome.

The ketone (1) on treatment with perbenzoic acid in the presence of catalytic amount of *p*-toluenesulphonic acid gave 3-oxa-4-oxo-*A*-homocholest-5-ene (4) and 3-oxa-4-oxo-*A*-homo-5-hydroxy-5α-cholestan-6β-yl chloride (5). The structures 4 and 5 were preferred over their 4-oxa analogues on the basis of pmr spectra. The signal at δ 4.23 and 4.2 for C2-H₂ in 4 and 5, respectively, indicated the presence of 3-oxa moiety⁶. In the case

Scheme 1

Compound 7 was analysed for C₂₇H₄₃O₃Cl. Its ir spectra showed the presence of oxido group